

Assessment of Digital Skills among TVET Tertiary Institution Lecturers in Kaduna State

Rabi Shehu Dalhatu, Maryam Muhammad Lawal & Aisha Haruna Bako
rabishehudalhatu@gmail.com 08034241807

The growing rate of youth unemployment in Nigeria underscores the urgency of equipping young people with relevant employability skills. This study assessed the digital skills possessed by TVET lecturers for integrating digitalization into training youths for employment, drawing on the quadruple helix model, which promotes collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society in fostering innovation and sustainable skill development. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. A survey research design was adopted, involving all 88 TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions offering TVET programmes in Kaduna state, without sampling. Data were collected using a self-developed 10-item questionnaire validated by experts in education. Reliability was confirmed through a pilot test, and cronbach alpha yielded a coefficient of 0.89. Administration of the instrument was carried out by the researcher with the help of two assistants, while mean, standard deviation, and t-test were used for analysis. The findings revealed that TVET lecturers in Kaduna state possessed very low levels of artificial intelligence education skills required for integrating digitalization in youth training. Moreover, years of teaching experience did not significantly influence their views. The study concluded that lecturers lack adequate digital skills for effectively preparing youths for employment. It was recommended that management of TVET institutions in Kaduna state adopt well-structured digital technology training and retraining strategies, guided by the quadruple helix approach, to build lecturers' artificial intelligence education skills and enhance youth employability.

Keywords:

Digital skills,
TVET,
Tertiary Institutions,
Lecturers,
Quadruple Helix Model

Introduction

The world is rapidly adjusting to digitalization, which has significantly transformed people's lives, daily routines, and occupational patterns. With the advent of digitalization, some traditional jobs are disappearing while new ones are emerging. Consequently, youths must acquire new sets of skills to remain relevant in digital workplaces. This development puts increasing pressure on educational institutions to re-examine the skills they

deliver to learners. Just as industries have evolved due to greater adoption of digital technologies, educational institutions are also upgrading their facilities and training approaches to meet new demands (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2021). To improve youth employability, Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) must digitalize its programmes to align with the needs of digital labour markets.

Digitalization refers to the use of digital technologies to enhance productivity and efficiency while reducing costs. Gray and Rumpe (2015) defined it as the application of digital technologies to transform business models and create new value. Within TVET, digitalization requires lecturers to adopt and apply emerging technologies to achieve instructional goals (Ebert-Stiftung, 2020). Commonly used tools include Learning Management Systems (LMS), synchronous technologies (audio, video, screen sharing, polls, and whiteboards), multimedia interactive platforms, cloud-based tools, and social participation technologies (Martin & Xie, 2022). Emerging digital technologies in TVET programmes, as noted by ILO (2019), include artificial intelligence (AI), extended reality (XR), augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and machine learning.

The advantages of digitizing TVET training programmes in tertiary institutions are extensive. Digital technologies facilitate effective planning, interactive learning, quick assessment, and the teaching of new employability skills (Martin & Xie, 2022). They also foster knowledge acquisition, teamwork, and critical thinking among students. Haleem, Javaid, Qadri, and Suman (2022) argued that tools such as virtual classrooms, augmented reality, and robotics not only make instruction engaging but also promote inclusive learning environments where performance data can be tracked. These technologies equally strengthen communication, collaboration, and problem-solving skills, qualities highly valued in the 21st-century labour market.

Beyond individual institutional efforts, the integration of the quadruple helix model which emphasizes collaboration among

academia, industry, government, and civil society is critical to advancing TVET digitalization. Through this model, TVET institutions can align their training strategies with labour market needs, industry innovation, and policy directions while engaging the wider community in skill development. This collaborative approach ensures that digital skills training is not confined to the classroom but connected to real-world applications and employment opportunities.

Digital skills encompass knowledge and competences for using computer systems, navigating the internet, engaging in online communication, and applying advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) in instruction. Snyder (2019) emphasized that TVET lecturers must possess AI skills such as using AI software to grade tests, customize teaching, design adaptive lesson plans, and create intelligent tutoring systems. These capabilities allow lecturers to individualize instruction, enhance student engagement, and prepare youths for complex digital work environments.

The acquisition of digital skills also supports communication, knowledge sharing, and technology-driven problem-solving (Pavel, Fruth, & Neacsu, 2015). As Nwazor and Nwaukwa (2015) noted, TVET lecturers' digital skills are essential for effective youth training in the digital age. TVET, as defined by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), is designed to provide knowledge, skills, and values relevant to diverse occupations within the Nigerian context. This includes business education, home economics, fine and applied arts, woodwork technology, building technology, electrical/electronic technology, and agricultural education, among others (Olaleye, 2021).

Nigeria's youthful population presents immense potential for shaping the country's economic future. Degryse (2016) observed that if adequately trained, Nigerian youths could benefit significantly from digitalization. yet, employers, policymakers, and parents continue to express concern about the limited capacity of TVET programmes in tertiary institutions to prepare young people for digital labour markets. recent statistics reveal the gravity of the problem: 13.9 million Nigerian youths aged 15–24 were unemployed in 2022 (NBS, 2022), while 23 million aged 15–34 were unemployed in 2020 (NBS, 2020).

In this 21st-century work environment, teaching experience may also influence how TVET lecturers perceive and utilize digital skills. Lecturers with more years of service may have different competencies compared to those with fewer years, due to variations in training and exposure. Against this backdrop, this study was undertaken to assess the digital skills possessed by TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions for integrating digitalization into youth training for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria, within the collaborative framework of the quadruple helix model.

Statement of the problem

Youth unemployment remains one of the most critical socio-economic challenges confronting Nigeria. To address this, the federal government introduced technical and vocational education and training (TVET) programmes in tertiary institutions with the objective of equipping young people with employable skills for wage employment or self-employment. Despite these efforts, youth unemployment persists at alarming levels, as consistently reported by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). Alarminglly, many TVET graduates are still

unable to secure jobs, thereby exacerbating Nigeria's unemployment situation.

The rapid transformation in the nature of work, driven by digitalization, has further increased the pressure on TVET programmes to integrate digital technologies in preparing youths for employment. This is crucial for reducing structural unemployment, which occurs when young people cannot respond adequately to the emerging digital job opportunities due to insufficient skills. Employers, parents, and policymakers have continued to express concern that graduates of TVET programmes in Nigerian universities lack the necessary digital competencies to take advantage of these opportunities. Consequently, questions arise about the quality and relevance of training delivered by TVET lecturers. The problem is often linked to factors such as an overemphasis on theoretical lessons, reliance on traditional teaching methods, and limited integration of digitalization into instructional delivery.

TVET lecturers play a central role in equipping the 21st-century youth with the digital skills needed for employment. However, reports from both national and international bodies such as NBS, the world bank, ILO, and UNESCO have consistently highlighted digital skills gaps among Nigerian youths, suggesting that TVET lecturers themselves may lack critical competencies required to effectively integrate digitalization in training. This challenge is particularly evident in regions like Kaduna state.

In addressing these gaps, the quadruple helix model provides a useful framework by emphasizing collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society in

enhancing skills development. Through such collaboration, TVET institutions can ensure that training is better aligned with labour market demands, technological innovations, and community needs. Despite its relevance, there is a scarcity of empirical research assessing the digital skills of TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions for integrating digitalization into youth training within this model, especially in Kaduna state. This study seeks to fill that gap.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine the status of digital skills possess by TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions for integrating digitalization in training youth with skills for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria. Specifically, this study ascertained the extent:

TVET lecturers possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youth with skills for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Research question

The following research question guided the study.

To what extent do TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at .05 level of significance:

There is no significance difference in the mean ratings of TVET lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in Kaduna

state, Nigeria. Based on years of teaching experience (1-5 years/6 years and above).

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design. It was carried out in Kaduna state, Nigeria. The population of TVET lecturers in public tertiary institutions in Kaduna state offering TVET programme. There was no sampling since the population was manageable and accessible to the researcher. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled “status of digital skills possessed by lecturers for integrating digitalization in training youths for employment (sdspl-idtye)”. The questionnaire consisted of two sections; and b. Section a contained one item on demographic information of the respondents such as years of teaching experience while section b contained 10 items in respect to the one research question and structured on a five point rating scale of very highly possessed (vhp) = 5, highly possessed (hp) = 4, moderately possessed (mp) = 3, lowly possessed (lp) = 2, and very lowly possessed (sd) = 1. Face and content validity of the instrument was determined using the opinions of two experts from technical and vocational education and training, and one expert from measurement and evaluation unit.

The reliability of the instrument was established using trail-test method and data collected were calculated with Cronbach alpha which yielded coefficient value of 89. The researcher, with the help of two research assistants adequately briefed and administered copies of the questionnaire to TVET lecturers in their institutions. On the spot distribution and collection of questionnaires was deployed and those who did not fill their instrument immediately were

revisited on another agreed date. Out of 88copies of questionnaire distributed, 83 (94%) of the copies were correctly filled and returned. Statistical mean and standard deviation were used to answer the researcher question and determined the homogeneity of respondents' views while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the p - value is less than 0.05 level of significance, otherwise, the null hypothesis was accepted. The data analysis was carried

out using Statistical Package For Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

Results

Research question 1

To what extent do TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions possess artificial intelligence (ai) education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria?

Table 1:mean ratings and standard deviation on the extent TVET lecturers possess ai education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths for employment

Sn	Artificial intelligence education skills	\bar{X}	Sd	Remarks
Ability to use:				
1	Grade scope ai tool to grade students' assignments and tests	1.48	.58	Very lowly possessed
2	Century ai platform to track students' progress while pointing out knowledge gaps in their learning	1.44	.64	Very lowly possessed
3	Century ai tools to reduce my academic workload	1.39	.71	Very lowly possessed
4	Digital tools such as analytics and web scanners to enhance teaching	1.53	.59	Lowly possessed
5	Intelligent tutoring systems (its) to handle feedback	1.40	.52	Very lowly possessed
6	Intelligent tutoring systems (its) to handle one-on-one teaching	1.40	.49	Very lowly possessed
7	Interactive virtual simulations to coach students in soft skills and self-development	1.47	.69	Very lowly possessed
8	Ai to create digital study guides and instructional snippets to enhance instructional delivery	1.41	.82	Very lowly possessed
9	Ai platform to create one-on-one personalized teaching experience for each student	1.51	.67	Lowly possessed
10	Interactive virtual simulations to aid students' life skills development	1.46	.52	Very lowly possessed
Cluster mean		1.45		Very lowly possessed

Field survey 2025

Table 2 revealed that out of the 10 artificial intelligence education skills listed for integrating digitalization, items 4 and 9 are lowly possess by TVET lecturers for integrating digitalization with mean scores ranged between 1.53 and 1.51 while the remaining eight items with mean scores ranging from 1.39 to 1.48. The cluster mean score of 1.45 shows that on the whole, TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions very lowly possess artificial intelligence education skills

for integrating digitalization in training youths for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Null hypothesis 1

There is no significance difference in the mean ratings of TVET lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Table 2: test significant difference of TVET lecturers on the extent they possess ai education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths for employment based on years of teaching experience

Years of experience	n	x	sd	df	t-value	p-value	decision
6 years and above	471	1.46	.84				
1-5 years	361	1.40	.68				
		811.52	1.00				not significant

Field survey 2025

Table 23 shows a t-value of 1.52 at 81 degree of freedom with a p-value of 1.00. Since the p-value of 1.00 is greater than the criterion value of .05 ($p\text{-value} = 1.00 > .05$), the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significance difference in the mean ratings of TVET lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria based on years of teaching experience

Discussion of findings

Findings of this revealed that TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions very lowly possess artificial intelligence education skills to integrate digitalization in training youth for

employment. It was specifically showed that TVET lecturers very lowly possess abilities to, use grade scope ai tool in grading students' assignments and tests, use century ai tool to track students' progress while pointing out knowledge gaps in their learning, use century ai tool to reduce academic workload, use intelligent tutoring systems (its) to handle feedback or handle one-on-one teaching among others. The findings of this study could be attributed to inadequate in-service programmes such as ICT workshops, seminars and conferences provided to TVET lecturers to up-date their skills in using emerging digital technologies such as ai to enhance their instructional delivery. It could also be due to lack or inadequate digital

technology infrastructures in TVET departments that prevent lecturers from adopting them in equipping students with 21st century skills for gainful employment. The findings of the study align with the position of Olutola and Olatoye (2018) that many lecturers in Nigeria need to be trained on digital skills in order to utilize digital technologies in enhancing teaching and learning in agreement, Kuni (2021), stressed that digitalization has exposed the poor digital skills among lecturers of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Additionally, Oviawe, Uwameiye and Uddin (2017) revealed that TVET in Nigeria was lagging behind in equipping youths with 21st century skills due to dearth of digital competent lecturers to use new technologies in teaching. In agreement, polit and Duktur (2022) observed that TVET institutions in Nigeria lack qualified ICT personnel. This contrasts the earlier findings of Ejinwa, Ojiaku and Nnaji (2021) which indicated that lecturers had a high level of digital technology skills that will allow them to be excellent instructors in the digital age.

Findings of the study also revealed that there was no significance difference in the mean ratings of TVET lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in Kaduna state, Nigeria based on years of teaching experience. It could be that both experience and inexperience TVET lecturers surveyed are not adequately provided with digital skills training programmes which could be the reason why both are of the same view that they very lowly possess AI education skills to integrate digitalization in training the youth for employment.

Conclusion

based on the findings of this study, the research concludes that TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions in Kaduna state do not possess enough digital skills to integrate digitalization in training the youth in skills for employment.

Recommendations

Base on the findings of this study, the researcher makes the following recommendations;

Management of TVET institutions in Kaduna state should adopt a well-articulated strategy for digital technology training and re-training of lecturers to enable them to acquire relevant artificial intelligence education skills to be able to equip youths with skills for gainful employment.

TVET lecturers in tertiary institutions in Kaduna state should search for suitable artificial intelligence training programs to update their artificial intelligence skills in order to remain relevant in the 21st century.

Federal and state government should formulate and ensure effective implementation of digital training programmes for TVET lecturers especially on emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, Extended Reality (XR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Virtual Reality (VR), among others. This will enable TVET lecturers to acquire skills in adopting these emerging technologies in enhancing youth acquisition of skills for gainful employment.

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